

Problem Based Learning Using Word Wall Website to Improve Students' Writing Achievement

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ABSTRACT: This current research aims to find out if there is any significant improvement in students' writing achievement after the students are taught through the modified Problem Based Learning using Word Wall Website (WWW). This is a quasi-experimental research design that conducts a quantitative method. The students were given writing tests, namely pre-test and post-test. There are 30 students in a class. The students were given treatments using modified method of PBL. The data are statistically analyzed through paired samples t-test in SPSS version 22. The finding shows that there is a significant improvement in students' writing achievement after the students were taught through the modified PBL. The score of post-test (72.90) is higher than pre-test (56.40) with the gain of 16.50. The t -value is 35.169 at the significant level of 0.000, which is lower than 0.05. It means, there is a significant improvement of students' writing achievement after the treatment. Then, it is suggested for teachers to apply this modified method in teaching writing, because this is a very good choice to boost students' writing achievement. This suggests further researchers to modify PBL with other technological media, such as video and song so that it can lead students to improve their writing achievement.

KEYWORDS: Game, Modified Problem Based Learning, Technology, Word Wall Website, Writing Achievement.

INTRODUCTION

Teaching writing in an EFL class is not an easy task for teachers. Though there are many methods to be applied, they always have the weaknesses. At present, the generation called 'Gen Z' who are students in schools is different from the previous generation. Their collective personality, thought processes, and educational tendencies are unique to traditional classroom practices and educational environments. The way how teachers teach is also changed. One of the solutions given in teaching writing is by using Problem Based Learning.

Problem based learning (PBL) is an instructional method where students learn by engaging in the process of solving real-world and problems. PBL was found by Barrows around 1969. Dastgeer, et al. (2015), PBL method is a more effective pedagogy method than traditional methods for improving English writing skill. From this statement, the researcher concludes that problem-based learning can make students more active and stimulate them to think more creatively to get their ideas in writing. The students can be encouraged to explore ideas and write or work in groups. Student who are reluctant to ask the teacher, can ask friends in the group or other groups.

Leong's (2009) study reveals that the weaknesses of PBL are that it is confusing for some students at first; some students are hesitant to discuss their thoughts about the problem, and it is difficult for teachers to arrange an open-ended problem for the learning process. Further, Ribeiro (2011) asserted that the implementation of PBL is difficult, it needs more time for preparation, and it is difficult to manage. Those are due to PBL needs an arrangement of an open-ended problem before its implementation and the obstacles found during its implementation, such as the losses perceived by the teacher, e.g., reduced control over content coverage and teaching-related workload.

Thus, the researcher intended to modify Problem Based Learning using Word Wall Website so that it can cover the weaknesses of the original PBL. Word Wall is an interactive game learning medium that is accessible online and has an attractive look. It is expected to attract student interest in learning because the game can be answered by students (Gandasari & Pramudiani in Novianti, et al., 2023).

Moreover, Swari (2023) states that Wordwall is one of the gamification platforms that can create a more joyful learning situation to improve students' interest, especially in reading skills. The integration of Wordwall within the teaching and learning process is believed to increase students' reading interest since it has various features that can create new learning material innovation. Since words play an important role in communication, mastering vocabulary makes it easier for students to create meaningful sentences. In this research, the researcher used word wall media in the features: random wheel and labeled diagram to increase writing achievement. The research question of this research is 'Is there any statistics significant improvement of the students' writing achievement after the students were taught through the Problem Based Learning using Word Wall Website?'. Furthermore, the objective of this research is to improve the students' writing achievement.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Byrne in Wibowo (2022) states that writing is more than just put the signs or symbols into a written form, but it needs to be arranged by following the process to form words, then those words are established into the sentences. Harmer (2004) divides the process of writing into four steps: planning; drafting; editing; and final version. Teaching writing means guiding the students to utter their ideas into a written form. Based on the curriculum, the students are taught about descriptive text in term of describing tourism places. According to Gerot and Wignell in Anggun (2016), descriptive text is a text type we use when we want to tell how something looks, smells, feels, acts, tastes, sound etc.

In this research, the researcher chose Problem Based Learning as a method to guide students in creating descriptive text by using Word Wall Website as the media. Cristine (2004) who proposed Word Wall, say that Word Wall media is a bulletin board display of vocabulary words grouped together in a way that makes sense to students. It allows students to see key words daily and use the visual support to deepen their understanding of new words. The purpose of teaching writing by using the Word Wall program is to provide students with a certain level of English vocabulary when writing descriptive texts. Since words play an important role in communication, mastering vocabulary makes it easier for students to create meaningful sentences. The researcher used word wall media in the features: random wheel and labeled diagram to overcome this problem to increase writing achievement.

This research uses the theory of Maastricht (1960s) about problem based learning steps for students to develop students' responsibilities, that is included in Schmidt (2011). Then, the researcher conducts problem based learning using word wall website. The differences between Maastricht's Problem Based Learning and the implementation of the Problem Based Learning using Word Wall Website in process approach are jotted below.

Table 1. The Differences between the original Problem Based Learning and Problem Based Learning using Word Wall Website

Process Approach	Problem Based Learning	Problem Based Learning using Word Wall Website
1.Planning	<p>1. Clarifying terms At the beginning of the session, the problem(s) should be presented to students. If you use paper cases one of the students read it aloud to get the group talking from the beginning. The first activity of the group should be the clarification of problems, terms and concepts not understood at first moment. The purpose of the first step is to agree on the meaning of the various words and terms and on the situation described in the problem. The use of problem-based learning can be made of the knowledge possessed by the group members or retrieved from a dictionary.</p>	<p>1. Clarifying terms At the beginning of the session, the problem(s) should be presented to students. Teacher shows a descriptive text in LCD Projector. She/he teaches the students about grammatical rules, generic structure, and social function of descriptive text. It also contains aspects of writing: content, organization, vocabulary, grammar and mechanics.</p>
	<p>2. Defining the problem Definition of the problem is the main goal during this</p>	<p>2. Defining the problem The teacher asks students to identify which one</p>

	<p>phase. The group should discuss and reach an agreement on the tricky events, which need explanation.</p> <p>Occasionally, a problem has been intentionally described on the way to test students' ability to recognize certain symptoms.</p> <p>Though they have some prior knowledge to recognize a problem, the prior knowledge doesn't allow them to resolve the problem straight away.</p>	<p>of name of place, address, sights, sounds, smells, textures, emotions to make descriptive text. Those words can help the students to generate a number of ideas. Then, teacher also explains how to write sentence (simple present tense). Teacher asks students to mention some tourism places in Lampung and write them down.</p>
2. Drafting	<p>3. Brainstorming</p> <p>This should result in ideas to structure the problem. Each individual may express his or her ideas free and without immediate discussion: it is important not to discuss and not to comment the ideas of others during this step, but to collect many ideas (prior knowledge). Together, students will compile ideas of the underlying circumstances of the problem (explanatory approach) and/or of implications arising from the problem (procedural approach).</p>	<p>3. Brainstorming</p> <p>The teacher introduces Word Wall Website and explains how to play the game. All of the students play this game use their own phones. The purpose of the third step is to agree on the meaning of the various words and terms and on the situation described in the problem. Use can be made of the knowledge possessed by the group members or retrieved from a dictionary.</p>
	<p>3. Editing</p>	<p>4. Structuring and hypothesis</p> <p>During this step, which forms the core of the analysis, the problem is explained on different ways. Ideas, which seem to be related, are worked out in relation to each other. Each group member is allowed to fully present ideas about matter. Group members can draw on all the prior knowledge they possess.</p> <p>This prior knowledge may be based on information acquired in earlier education, facts and insights obtained by reading different articles or on another way. The other members of the group and the tutor are allowed to probe the students' knowledge to the full, to introduce other explanations and question certain opinions. The process of brainstorming and discussion is a collaborative approach. It leads to more creativity and output than each member of the group could generate on his own.</p> <p>5. Learning objectives</p> <p>Each group reaches consensus on the learning objectives; tutor ensures learning objectives are focused, achievable, comprehensive, and appropriate. So, the main aim of this step is to formulate learning objectives on which group will concentrate their activities during phase six. In this stage it is possible to use conceptual map as a tool for research summary, making associations, integrating information and proceeding information and transferring it to long-term knowledge, but also a tool</p>

for defying new learning objectives.

terms of learning objectives and based on the level of students.

6. Searching for Information

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This phase is supposed to provide answers to the questions evoked in the problem-analysis phase and offer students possibility to acquire a more profound knowledge of theories at the root of the problem. The group members collect information individually with respect of defined learning objectives.

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PBL is also important because it gives possibility to students to find their own resources.

7. Synthesis

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Group shares results of private study. The tutor checks learning and may assess the group. So, the final step is synthesizing and testing the newly acquired information. They also discussed whether they now acquired more proficient, accurate, detailed explanation and understanding about what is going on behind the problem.

Each group presents the result of the written form to other groups. The teacher helps students to reflect or evaluate on their investigation and the processes they use.

If some of the students haven't understood the issues well, task of other students is to try to explain them methodology of their work.

4.Final Version

In this step it would be necessary for the certain types of the problems to check for students' decision-making process and the algorithm behind their decisions.

8. Feedback

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It includes feedback of all students on the case, the process and the tutor, to improve the learning process. Also, it is very important the students validate the course and give their comments on the quality of the problem as well as on the quality of the group process and the tutor's performance.

From student feedback, teacher gets information about whether the learning activities are effective and acceptable to all students or not. Thus, a teacher can take corrective actions if there is something that is deemed lacking in implementing the new learning process.

The word wall website was used in Problem Based Learning for solving the stated problems above because the word wall website as visual media hopefully could give the opportunities for students to visualize and develop ideas easily and also elaborate students' ideas easier than text in writing a text, especially descriptive text. By using technology, the students felt more enjoyable and interested in the learning process. The researcher believed that applying the Problem Based Learning using Word Wall Website could increase the students' writing achievement in descriptive text.

METHODOLOGY

To answer the formulated research questions, the researcher conducted a quantitative study in the form of one-group pre-test-post-test design.

Figure 1. Research Design

T1 X T2

T1 = Pre-test
 X = Treatment
 T2 = Post-test

The figure above illustrates that pre-test is administered before the treatment to obtain information about the students' writing achievement which is prior to the treatment. The researcher then gives the treatments which entail teaching writing through the modified PBL at one class. Afterward, a post-test is given to see the difference of students' writing achievement as a result of the treatments.

PARTICIPANTS

Participants of this research are one class of the 8th grade C of SMP N 9 Bandar Lampung that consisted of 30 students. It was chosen by using an interview to one of the English teachers in that school. It was known that the students of the class had low score in writing. They seemed to be in the beginner level of English.

INSTRUMENT

The researcher used one instrument to collect the data, i.e. writing test that was divided into pre-test and post-test. The tests are based on the aspects of writing by Jacob, et al. (1981). Below are the elaborations as the construct validity of this research.

Table 3.2 Scoring Rubric for Writing Test by Jacob, et al (1981)

Content	30 – 27	Excellent to very good	Knowledgeable, through development of thesis, relevant to the topic
	26 – 22	Good to average	Some knowledge of subject, limited development of thesis, mostly relevant to the topic, but lack details.
	21 – 17	Fair to poor	Fair to poor limited knowledge of subject, inadequate development of topic.
	16 – 13	Very poor	Very poor does not show knowledge of subject, not enough to evaluate.
Organization	20 – 18	Excellent to very good	Ideas clearly stated, well-organized, logical sequencing, cohesive.
	17 – 14	Good to average	Loosely organized but main idea stand out , limited support, logical but incomplete sequencing.
	13 – 10	Fair to poor	Ideas confused or disconnected, lack logical sequencing and development.
	9 – 7	Very poor	No organization, not enough to evaluate.
Vocabulary	20 – 18	Excellent to very good	Sophisticated range, effective word choice, word form mastery
	17 – 14	Good to average	Adequate range, sometimes errors of word choice, usage but meaning not obscured.
	13 – 10	Fair to poor	Frequent errors of word choice, usage but meaning confused or obscured
	9 – 7	Very poor	Essentially translation, little knowledge of English vocabulary, not enough to evaluate.
Language Use	25 – 22	Excellent to very good	Effective complex constructions, few errors of agreement, tense, number, word order, articles, pronouns and prepositions.
	21 – 18	Good to average	Effective but simple constructions, minor problems in complex constructions, several errors of agreement, tense, number, word order, articles, pronouns and prepositions.

Mechanics	17 – 11	Fair to poor	Major problem in simple/complex constructions, frequent errors of negation, agreement, tense, number, word order, articles, pronouns and prepositions, meaning confused and obscured.
	10 – 5	Very poor	Almost no mastery of sentence construction rules, dominated by errors, does not communicative, not enough to evaluate.
	5	Excellent to very good	Few errors of spelling, punctuation, capitalization, and paragraphing.
	4	Good to average	Occasional errors of spelling, punctuation, capitalization, and paragraphing.
	3	Fair to poor	Frequent errors of spelling, punctuation, capitalization, and paragraphing.
	2	Very poor	Dominated by error.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The research question is: ‘Is there any statistics significant improvement of the students’ writing achievement after the students were taught through the Problem Based Learning using Word Wall Website?’. The researcher calculated the data of the post-test and pre-test. Through paired sample t-test, the data were truly computed to seek whether there is a significant difference in the students’ writing achievement of the students who are taught through the modified PBL using WWW. The following table is the result of the Paired Samples T-Test.

Table 3. Paired Samples T-Test

	Paired Differences	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)					
					Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
								Lower	Upper
Pair 1 Post-test Pre-test	16.50000 2.56972 .46916 15.54045 17.45955	35.169	29	.000					

From the tables above, the post-test and the pre-test are compared. The mean difference between the tests is 16.50. It means that there is a difference between the pre-test and post-test. Moreover, the sig (2-tailed) is 0.000. It is lower than 0.05. 0.05 is the decision threshold. If the value is less than 0.05, the result is considered significant, while if it is greater, the result is considered not significant. It can be concluded that there is a significant difference between the post-test towards the pre-test. The hypothesis (H₁) is then accepted. Equally, it proves that there is a significant improvement in students’ writing achievement after the students are taught through the Problem Based Learning using Word Wall Website.

This proves the theory of Cristine (2004) who says that Word Wall media is a bulletin board display of vocabulary words grouped together in a way that makes sense to students. It allows students to see key words daily and use the visual support to deepen their understanding of new words. Word wall media is a part of visual media. Students may learn more easily and retain information when using visual media. It successfully helped the students broaden up their mind. **Related to the Cognitive Load Theory (Sweller, 1988)**, the design of Wordwall activities (short tasks, repetition, visual aids) helps reduce cognitive overload, making it easier for students to focus on learning specific English language skills.

When the original Problem Based Learning was modified with word wall website, the weakness could be covered. By modifying this method, the students were not only active in the discussion that talked about a problem, but also influenced by the word wall website that brought technological touch to students where they felt so happy in doing the learning activities. This is in line with a research by Kepekisan (2024), who examines the application of technology-integrated PBL methods as an approach to improve

students' writing skill. The research shows a positive impact of the application of problem-solving technology on increasing students' knowledge. Research and innovation supported by the latest and technology has changed students' writing patterns, creating a more effective and enjoyable learning experience.

The advantages of using word wall website had cover a weakness of PBL where some students are struggled to cope with the problem in PBL that they had never done before, that often occurred in the early stage of Problem-Based. The improvement of writing skill occurred because the modified method utilized an up-to-date technology that made the students enjoy the learning activities. They felt fun and happy when using the word wall website, because they could play a game while studying. The various features of the website which consisted of the colours, pictures and games made the students rise many ideas. It eased them to construct sentences with the new vocabularies in the website, even the students got easier to create a descriptive text. This is supported by a research done by Marensi, et al. (2023) who conducts a classroom action research about word wall media. The advantage that students get from using word wall-based media is that students who were initially lazy, tired and slow to follow the learning process in class, now look active when learning takes place.

Moreover, the most affected aspect that rose the highest of all was vocabulary. WWW provide many new words to the user. Understanding the meaning of the words were also provided with pictures and games like *find the match*. In the pre-test, students wrote a short descriptive text. While in the post-test, their vocabulary was getting more. They knew the new words by playing the games. It helped them construct sentences, even a descriptive text. There were also many pictures to help them understand what the meaning of the words were. This is why it is related to the theory of Cristine (2004), who introduced the Word Wall concept, describes it as a bulletin board that showcases vocabulary words arranged in a way that holds significance for students. This visual tool allows students to consistently engage with key terms, thus improving their understanding through visual support. Word Wall, as a visual medium, facilitates enhanced learning and improves information retention among students.

Thus, the modified PBL method using WWW can improve students' writing ability. Based on the results, there is a significant improvement in students' writing achievement after the students are taught through Problem Based Learning using Word Wall Website.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Based on the results of this research, it can be concluded that the implementation of the modified PBL using WWW significantly improved students' writing achievement. Wordwall can be used to create structured learning paths with prompts and hints to guide students through the problem-solving process. WWW also **streamlines the learning process**. By providing pre-designed activities and resources, Wordwall can save time and effort for both students and educators, making PBL more manageable.

Based on the condition occurred when this research was held, the researcher suggests teachers that they have to be creative in applying the modified method of PBL using WWW because it can only be implemented in the schools that have technological stuffs like laptop, internet connection, projector and audio. This might be a limitation in classes with unsophisticated media. The effective implementation of the modified method relies on the capability of the school that can provide technology. To enrich the modification, it is suggested for further researchers to modify the problem based learning method with other technological media, such as videos and songs that can lead students to be joyful in learning English.

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